

PATTERNED GLASS FIBER SURFACES – ROUTE TO INTERFACE MODIFICATION?

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ABSTRACT

Morphology and physicochemical properties of the fiber-matrix interface play a significant role in determining the properties of composite materials. This work reports the results of surface modification of glass fibers by formation of patterns that vary in chemical functionalities. Commercially available E-glass fibers, approximately 17 μm in diameter are patterned using photolithography. Subsequent to patterning, the glass fibers are functionalized with a highly hydrophobic fluoro silane molecule. Single fiber contact angle measurements using dynamic Wilhelmy method show a well-defined transition in contact angle from 100° to 50° between the patterns. This confirms the patterned surface modification of glass fibers with two different chemical functionalities of hydrophobic and hydrophilic sequences along its length.

1. INTRODUCTION

Fiber reinforced composites are an important class of engineering materials owing to their lightweight, high specific strength and stiffness, excellent thermal and chemical stability. Their performance is controlled by the properties of the fiber, matrix and fiber-matrix interface, with each fiber-matrix combination offering its own synergism of properties. A composite made from a strong fiber-matrix combination may not essentially be strong as the overall properties are also governed by its interface. [1] Interface is a region formed by the common boundary of the continuous matrix and the reinforcing fiber, possessing its own physical and mechanical properties different from that of its constituents. Shear stress transfer between the matrix and reinforcement occurs by a combination of mechanical inter-locking, physical adhesion and chemical bonding. Physical adhesion of a surface is controlled by its surface free energy, which in a composite is attributed to the thermodynamic work of adhesion between the fiber and matrix. [2, 3]

Recent research has focused much attention on tailoring the physicochemical properties of the fiber-matrix interface. The two most common methods for tailoring the interface in fiber-reinforced composites are: (i) Chemical modification of the constituents, resulting in enhanced bonding and/or adhesion and (ii) Topographical modification which presents an increase in interfacial surface area for stress transfer to occur. Strategies for interface tailoring include

application of sizing or surface coating on fibers, incorporation of nano particles or use of reactive oligomers that can enhance fiber-matrix interactions. [4] Most attempts in interface engineering deals with homogenous modification of either the fiber or the bulk matrix. However, earlier reports [5] also suggest that a composite containing both strong and weak regions at the fiber-matrix interface exhibits high strength and toughness simultaneously.

This article reports preliminary results related to the patterned surface modification of glass fibers using the micro fabrication technique of photolithography. Micro fabrication is the process of creating miniature structures on surfaces that are in the order of micro and nano meter scales. The most important micro fabrication techniques include photo and soft lithography, thin film growth and deposition, etching and bonding. These techniques are widely used in medicine, pharmaceuticals and electronics for the fabrication of desired structures on a variety of surfaces. [6] Of the many different fabrication techniques available, photolithography is one of the most often employed method owing to its high resolution and ease of applicability on a variety of surfaces. [7]

In this work, glass fibers coated with a photopolymer are exposed to ultra violet (UV) light through a mask, resulting in the formation of desired patterns on the fiber surface. The patterned fiber is then functionalized with a fluoro silane, rendering the fiber with alternating hydrophobic and hydrophilic sequences along its length. The morphology of such modified glass fibers is observed under a Scanning Electron Microscope. Wetting behavior of the surface modified fibers is studied using a single fiber tensiometer by the Wilhelmy technique.

2. EXPERIMENTAL

2.1 Surface modification of glass fibers

Among a variety of fibrous reinforcements available, glass fibers (E-glass fibers, Syncoglass NV, Belgium) has been chosen due to the balance between its fiber properties and surface chemistry.

2.2.a Cleaning and activation of glass fibers

The first step of cleaning and activating the E - glass fibers has been done following procedures reported in [8], with minor modifications. A small bundle of glass fibers, approximately 5cm long was cut from the bobbin and de-greased using dichloromethane (Alfa Aesar) for one hour. Following the cleaning process, the fibers were treated using a basic piranha solution for two hours at 65°C and dried under vacuum at 100°C. This process renders a clean and hydroxyl rich fiber surface.

2.2.b Micro-patterning and silane formation on glass fibers

The cleaned and activated glass fiber bundle was carefully separated into individual fibers and glued to a glass slide. The fibers were then dip coated with a commercially available photosensitive polymer (ma-P 1275 HV, Micro resist Technology GmbH, Germany). Subsequently, the photopolymer coated fibers was exposed to UV light (wavelength $\lambda = 365$ nm) for five minutes and then rinsed with an aqueous alkaline solution. The mask consists of a pattern composed of transparent and opaque regions. Upon exposure to UV light, the photopolymer under the transparent regions undergo degradation while the material under the opaque regions remain unchanged. Thus, a fiber surface consisting of segments covered with the photo polymer and pristine glass fiber surface is formed as a result of photolithography.

As the last step, patterned fibers are functionalized with 1H, 1H, 2H, 2H-Perfluorodecyltrichlorosilane (ABCRCR, Germany; short name: FDTS) via solution deposition. Patterned glass fibers were immersed in a 10 mM FDTS solution prepared in extra dry n-heptane (Sigma Aldrich, water <0.001%). Fluoro silane functionalization of the glass fibers was carried

out for two hours at room temperature under inert atmosphere. The fibers were removed from the reaction mixture and washed several times with acetone and ethanol to remove physically adsorbed FDTS, followed by drying at 100 °C for two hours under vacuum. Washing with acetone and ethanol also removed the unexposed photopolymer, resulting in patterned fiber surfaces containing fluorine functional hydrophobic and hydroxyl functional hydrophilic groups. All fiber samples were stored in a nitrogen purged desiccator until further use.

Characterization techniques

2.3.a Electron Microscopy

To assess the surface morphology of the as received E-glass fibers, cleaned and activated fibers, FDTS grafted and patterned fibers; Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) was used. Single fibers were directly placed on a conductive carbon tape and coated with a thin layer of platinum using a sputter coater to avoid charging effects. Electron microscopy imaging was performed with a XL-30 Philips scanning electron microscope at an operating voltage of 20 kV.

2.3.b Contact angle measurement : Dynamic Wilhelmy method

In order to study the wetting properties of the glass fibers resulting from the treatments and the patterning process, dynamic contact angle measurements was performed using a force tensiometer (K100SF, Kruss GmbH, Germany). Figure 1 shows a schematic for the dynamic contact angle measurement of single fibers by the Wilhelmy method.

Figure 1: Schematic of contact angle measurement of single fibers using dynamic Wilhelmy method

The sample, a single fiber is attached to a wire hook by using an adhesive tape and suspended from a microbalance (resolution 0.1 μg) and is immersed into the testing liquid at the desired immersion speed. Force as a function of immersion depth is measured and by knowing the perimeter of the fiber and surface tension of the test liquid, the contact angle can be calculated using equation (1).

$$F = P * \gamma_L * \cos \theta \quad (1)$$

where θ is the dynamic contact angle ($^\circ$), F is the force measured by the microbalance (mN), P the perimeter of the fiber (m) and γ_L is the vapor/liquid surface tension (mN/m). A typical force vs. immersion depth curve obtained during the contact angle measurements is as shown in figure 2.

Figure 2: (Color online) typical force vs. immersion depth plot obtained as the fiber is immersed and retracted from the test liquid

To measure the perimeter of the fiber, hexane (surface tension 18.2 mN/m, temperature 25°C) is used as the test liquid. Force is recorded as the fiber is immersed into and emerged from hexane. Assuming conditions of perfect wetting and hence zero contact angle, the perimeter of the fiber is calculated using equation 1. To assess the wettability of the fibers resulting from the different treatments and patterning process, a single fiber approximately 10 mm in length is immersed at a measuring speed of 1 mm/min into the test liquid (milliQ water, surface tension: 72.8 mN/m) at 25°C. Force is measured as a function of immersion depth and the advancing and receding contact angles are calculated from equation (1). All values reported herein are measurements on single fibers and is the average of at least three measurements.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Morphological analysis

Figure 3 a, b, and c depicts the surfaces of as received, cleaned-activated and homogeneously silane functionalized glass fibers, respectively as observed under the scanning electron microscopy.

The as-received E-glass fiber surfaces (fig. 3a) show presence of residual silicon dioxide and protective sizing applied during the production process. Figure 3(b) shows a homogeneously clean and smooth fiber surface, indicating that the cleaning procedure employed has been efficient. The resulting neat fiber surface could be explained as a result of extraction of the production residues while being treated with the degreasing and activation agents. It is to be noted that no cracks or other forms of defects are observed on the fiber surface after chemical degreasing and activation treatments. Figure 3(c) represents the morphology of FDTs grafted glass fiber. The image shows a reasonably good coverage of the perfluoro silane on the fiber surface. Modification with perfluoro silane generates tiny mountain-like protrusions fiber surface, which is characteristic for the silane condensation resulting from the reaction of the silane head group with hydroxyl groups of the glass fiber, leading to the formation of a stable R-Si-O bond. This observation is similar to previous reports. [7]

Figure 3: (a) E- glass fiber (b) cleaned/activated fiber (c) FDTs grafted glass fiber

Figure 4 represents the surface morphology of patterned glass fiber. The bright portion on the left side of the image represents the area of the fiber grafted with FDTs while the grey area represents the surface of the pristine glass fiber.

Figure 4: SEM image of a patterned glass fiber: (a) Grafted with FDTs layer and (b) Pristine fiber surface

During the photolithography process, fibers coated with the photo polymer were exposed to UV light through a mask, resulting in patterns along the length of the fiber. Upon immersion into FDTs solution, the pristine fiber surface containing silanol groups reacts with the head group of the fluoro silane while the portions covered by the photopolymer does not allow adsorption of fluoro silane molecules. Rinsing the fibers using acetone and ethanol post silanisation results in removal of the unexposed photopolymer and physically adsorbed FDTs. Thus, the process leads to the modification of the glass fibers, resulting in a fiber surface with a gradient topography varying in both chemical functionalities and surface roughness.

3.2 Dynamic contact angle measurements using single fiber Wilhelmy method

The bar chart below in figure 5 presents a comparison of the advancing and receding angles water contact angle and contact angle hysteresis for the as received, cleaned and activated and homogenously FDTs grafted glass fibers.

Advancing angle values are obtained when the fiber is immersed into the test liquid, resulting in pinning of contact angle while the receding angles are obtained when the fiber is withdrawn from the liquid. Contact angle hysteresis is given by the difference between the advancing and receding contact angles. The difference between the two angles occurs due to presence of metastable state as the liquid

advances and recedes over the surface, resulting in intrinsic contact angles due to varied surface roughness and chemical inhomogeneities.

Figure 5: (Color online) Advancing and receding contact angles, hysteresis for as received, pristine (degreased/activated) and FDTs grafted glass fiber respectively

As received E-glass fibers exhibit a high degree of contact angle hysteresis, which could be due to surface structural variations and chemical inhomogeneity. Freshly cleaned and activated glass fibers exhibit low advancing and receding contact angles and hence, a low contact angle hysteresis. Low contact angle values result from the formation of superficial hydroxyl groups capable of forming hydrogen bonds with water, which favors wetting and renders a hydrophilic surface. A low value for the contact angle hysteresis indicates a homogeneously smooth and pure fiber surface, which is in good agreement with the surface analysis of such fibers observed under SEM. FDTs grafted surfaces exhibit a good degree of hydrophobicity, resulting from the low surface free energy of the perfluoroalkyl based silane. However, a considerably higher degree of hysteresis could result from a large variation in surface roughness, which could also be seen as small peaks on the surface of FDTs grafted fibers, resulting from silane condensation.

Figure 6 shows the variation of force and advancing contact angle as a function of immersion depth of a patterned glass fiber. A sharp increase in force is observed from negative or almost to zero to approximately 2×10^{-3} mN. Negative force indicates contact angle values between 90° and 180° , thus confirming poor wetting of the fiber surface with water. This observation confirms the existence of wettability gradient along the length of the glass fiber, perceived to be from the formation of patterns varying in chemical and topographical functionalities. The region of the fiber functionalized by the fluoro silane layer after formation of patterns is hydrophobic due to change in its hydration state. However, the pristine fiber surface exhibits higher contact angles in comparison to a freshly cleaned glass surface, which could be due to fiber surface contamination.

Figure 6: (color online) Force and advancing contact angle for a patterned glass fiber as a function of immersion depth

4. CONCLUSIONS

The present work shows a possible methodology for the patterned surface modification of glass fibers using photolithography. The dynamic wetting properties of modified fibers measured using the Wilhelmy technique shows a well-defined transition between the hydrophobic and hydrophilic patterns along the length of the modified fibers. Scanning electron microscopy analysis of modified fibers reveals the formation of a reasonably homogenous and smooth perfluoro silane functionalized fiber surface. Thus, a patterned glass fiber surface composed of fluorine and hydroxyl functionalities has been fabricated and tested in this work.

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